

“The Analytical Impact of the Indira Mahila Yojana on the Socio-Economic Status of Women SHG’s in Maharashtra”

Dr.Gopal S. Gawai

Assistant Professor

PSGVPM’S, Arts, Science and Commerce College, Shahada, Dist. Nandurbar.

Mob. No. 7972220497, E-Mail: prof.gsgawai@gmail.com

Introduction:

The experiment of SHG was firstly started by Mysore Resettlement and Development Agency (MYRADA) in India on the basis of SHG development in Bangladesh and after that the movement of SHGs spread all over the India.

The self-help groups have ancient traditions in India historical as well as prehistoric era, there is evidence that such groups existed. Thousands of such groups are operating in rural and urban areas of India. The aim of self-help groups to eradicate poverty and unemployment, establishing such groups on the basis of self-reliance and mutual support rather than waiting for someone else. In India, job creation is a major problem and it is impossible for everyone to get permanent jobs in the organized sector. In India, there are two major types of self-help group’s i. e. Micro finance group and self-help groups. The micro finance groups work in savings and debt allocation while self-help groups do other programs to increase their incomes with regular savings. It mainly works for the production of garments, food processing, and production of products by using local technology. The role of non-governmental organizations or NGOs or similar mechanisms is very important in this type of entrepreneurship. In India, such organizations are doing well in various states.

Therefore, it is imperative to increase their income through self-help groups to increase their family income, increase their living standards, self-esteem, self-reliance, decision making and fearlessness. Lastly it helps women to become economically, socially and politically empowered through SHGs.

Keywords: SHG’S, Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurship, MAVIM and Economic Development.

Review of Related Literature:

Received: 12 January 2026

Revised: 4 February 2026

Accepted: 12 February 2026

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/2026/s13/15>

A. Venkatachalam and A. Jeyapragash (2004) in their work, “Self Help Groups in Dindigul District,” found that the total savings of the SHG members in Dindigul District amount to Rs.622.99 lakhs. The Sangha Loan sanctioned to its members is in tune of 4.3 times of savings. In words, the total amount of Sangha loan sanctioned is Rs.27.20 lakhs. The SHGs in Dindigul District have made a silent revolution for the economic empowerment of poor rural women.

M. Soundarapandian (2006) in his study “Micro Finance for Rural Entrepreneurs Issues and Strategies” made an attempt to analyse the growth of the SHGs and the role of microfinance in developing the rural entrepreneurship. The study suggests that though there is a positive growth rate of the SHGs in states get in terms of growth of the SHGs there is wide variation among states. Linkages of banks with the SHGs are found impossible for this variation.

Ravindra C. Satpute (2012) in his research on “Micro-Finance: A Critical Study of Need, Practices and Future Trends (With Special Reference to Self Help Groups of Amravati District)”, he selected the sample of 400 SHGs in activities like Phenile making, Candle, Agarbatti making, Pickle and Papad making, etc. and found that the maximum number 273 (69.46%) of respondents joined the group for their overall economic development. he further stated that loan amount used by the respondents for domestic purpose, asset building and agriculture respectively. Only 63.07% of the total SHG’s get the benefits from various government schemes.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To analyze the growth of Indira MahilaYojana andSwayamsidha scheme forwomen SHG’s in Maharashtra.
2. To study the socio-economic status of women SHG’s under Swayamsidha scheme in Maharashtra
3. To study the effective support of the government on women SHG’s.

Indira MahilaYojana:

According to the report of director of MAVIM “the Indira MahilaYojana was implemented by the Central Government from 1994 and the MahilaSamruddhi Programme was merged with it and a revised Swayamsiddha Programme was declared for implementation for 5 years from 2001 - 2002 onwards. MAVIM implements the Swayamsiddha Programme in 19

districts and 36 Blocks in Maharashtra. Out of 36 blocks, 21 blocks (old) of Indira Mahila Yojana and 15 new blocks were selected. A target of forming 3,500 self-help groups was to be formed by the end of 2006, in 19 districts where the programme operated” and “sauchalayas were to be constructed with 40% contribution by the members of the village and 60% contribution from Company’s own funds obtained from Government of Maharashtra under Swayamsidha scheme.”

At the end of “March 2005, 3797 SHG groups were formed and 47760 women were organised. The women saved `2.42 crores and generated internal lending of `2.34 crores. They obtained bank loans of `87 lakhs. 2237 women started their own business.”

According to the report of MAVIM “at the end of March 2007, 3943 SHG groups were formed and 50,066 women were organised. The SHG members saved `5.70 crores and generated an internal lending of `10.31 crores. They obtained bank loans of `12.65 crores and 17,734 women started their own business.”

Year wise Growth of SHG under Swayamsidhha Scheme of MAVIM

According to the data table (4.7) growth of SHGs were ranged from 76.69% to 0.00% during the years 2003 to 2017. The highest ratio of SHGs formed by MAVIM under Swayamsidhha scheme in Maharashtra was into the year of 2004 i.e. 76.69% whereas the negative growth was observed during 2007, 2008, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2014 and 2015 (i.e.-0.53%, -12.90%, -6.09%, -2.65%, -11.66%, -18.92% and -23.47%).

Table 4.7: Year wise Growth of SHG under Swayamsidhha Scheme of MAVIM

Years	Swayamsidhha		
	SHG	Cumulative Frequency	Growth of SHG
OpeningBal.	--	2,149	--
2004	1,648	3797	76.69%
2005	126	3923	3.32%
2006	20	3943	0.51%
2007	-21	3922	-0.53%
2008	-506	3416	-12.90%
2009	0	3416	0.00%
2010	-208	3208	-6.09%
2011	-85	3123	-2.65%
2012	-364	2759	-11.66%
2013	0	2759	0.00%
2014	-522	2,237	-18.92%
2015	-525	1,712	-23.47%
2016	0	1,712	0.00%
2017	0	1,712	0.00%

Source: 1. Report of The Comptroller and Auditor General of India, for the year ended 2009
 2. Economic Survey of Maharashtra (2008-09 to 2013-14)
 3. Reports of MAVIM (2014 to 2017)

Table no.1: Profile of Women’s Entrepreneurs in Aurangabad District

	Manufacturing		Trading		Service		Overall	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Age group								
Below 25	1	7%	0	0%	0	0%	1	2
25 - 30	4	27%	3	21%	9	43%	17	33.3
31 - 40	6	40%	4	29%	4	19%	14	27.5
41 - 50	2	13%	6	43%	5	24%	13	25.5
51 and Above	2	13%	1	7%	3	14%	6	11.8
Community								
SC	1	7%	1	7%	1	5%	3	6
ST	2	13%	1	7%	6	29%	9	18
OBC	3	20%	2	14%	2	10%	7	14
VJNT	5	33%	7	50%	1	5%	13	26
Open	4	27%	3	21%	11	52%	18	36
General education								
Not attended the school	4	27%	3	21%	4	19%	11	22
Primary	3	20%	1	7%	0	0%	4	8
Secondary	1	7%	5	36%	14	67%	20	40
Higher secondary	5	33%	1	7%	0	0%	6	12
Graduation	2	13%	3	21%	3	14%	8	16
Post-Graduation	0	0%	1	7%	0	0%	1	2
Technical education of women entrepreneurs								
Nil	9	60%	11	79%	13	62%	33	66
Certificate	5	33%	3	21%	7	33%	15	30
Diploma	1	7%	0	0%	1	5%	2	4
SHG members trained								
Not Trained	1	7%	0	0%	2	10%	3	6
1 to 5	4	27%	6	43%	2	10%	12	24
6 to 10	8	53%	7	50%	12	57%	27	54
Above 10	2	13%	1	7%	5	24%	8	16

Source: Field survey

The MAVIM implemented Swayamsiddha programme under the assistant of women and child development department ministry in Maharashtra. The manufacturing activities carried out by respondents had ratio of 2.0%, 8.0%, 18.0% and 2.0% related to the garments manufacturing, agriculture, livelihood and other manufacturing activities respectively. The trading related activities such as fancy and general stores, cloth and garments, ladies’ accessories and other trading activities had ratio of 6.0%, 8.0%, 10.0%, and 4.0%. The ratio

Received: 12 January 2026

Revised: 4 February 2026

Accepted: 12 February 2026

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/2026/s13/15>

of 14.0%, 4.0%, 20.0%, 2.0% and 2.0% respondents had into beauty parlors, caterings, tailoring and training institute, floriculture and other service activities related to the service sector. The age group of women in Swayamsidha had ratio of 2.0% (1), 33.3% (17), 27.5% (14), 25.5% (13) and 11.8% (6) respondents had into the age group of below 25, 25 – 30, 31 – 40, 41 – 50 and 51 and above respectively. The category of women had ratio of 6.0% (3), 18.0% (9), 14.0% (7), 26.0% (13) and 36.0% (18) respondents into the category of SC, ST, OBC, NT and Open respectively. The respondents had ratio of 22.0%, 8.0%, 40.0%, 12.0%, 16.0% and 2.0% respondent's illiterate, Primary, Secondary, Higher secondary, Graduation and Post-graduation education completed.

Table no.4: Amount of Sales, Capital Invested and Loan borrow

	Manufacturing		Trading		Service		Overall	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Amount of Sales at the initial stage								
0- `10000	1	7%	3	21%	3	14%	7	14
`10000-30000	2	13%	4	29%	3	14%	9	18
`30000-50000	2	13%	3	21%	1	5%	6	12
`50000-70000	7	47%	2	14%	9	43%	18	36
Above `70000	3	20%	2	14%	5	24%	10	20
Amount of Capital Invested (Rs. in lakhs)								
Upto 1	2	13%	5	36%	2	10%	9	18
1 to 2	0	0%	0	0%	1	5%	1	2
2 to 3	1	7%	1	7%	2	10%	4	8
3 to 5	3	20%	2	14%	2	10%	7	14
5 and above	9	60%	6	43%	14	67%	29	58

Source: Field survey

The Amount of Sales at the initial stage under Swayamsidha scheme ratio of 14.0% (7), 18.0% (9), 12.0% (6), 36.0% (18) and 20.0% (10) respondents had sale into the group of up to `10000, `10000-30000, `30000-50000, `50000-70000 and Above `70000 respectively. The Amount of Capital Invested (Rs. in lakhs) had ratio of 18.0% (9), 2.0% (1),

8.0% (4), 14.0% (7) and 58.0% (29) respondents invested amount of capital up to ₹ 20000, ₹ 20000-30000, ₹ 30000-40000, ₹ 40000-50000 and Above ₹ 50000 respectively.

Conclusion

According to the data table it is well seen that the participation of women in economic activities increased and also positively seen their entrepreneurial development in Maharashtra. The number of members does not increase under scheme due to norms of MAVIM. Lastly, we can conclude that MAVIM putting its effort at great extents to upliftment of women and bringing them into the main stream of economic development.

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